
3D Object Models: Smartphone Applications Vs Non – contact Portable Coordinate Measuring Machines

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Abstract

In 2025, surveying engineers make use of state-of-the-art technologies for effective three-dimensional modeling that features satisfactory levels of accuracy and speed. Remarkably, the applications based on smartphones for 3D modeling are characterized by ease of access and affordability. The basis of this research is to highlight the methodologies behind these smartphone applications along with their respective web-platforms and comparing them, concerning accuracy, to Non-contact PCMMs.

Polycam, a widely used platform, was chosen for analysis. Tests were conducted using Android (Samsung A52 5G) and iPhone (16 Pro Max) smartphones, as well as a Nikon Mirrorless Digital Camera (Nikon Z50) via Polycam's web-platform version. Four objects of varying materials - a wooden owl figurine, a clay pot, a plaster cast of a statuette and a plastic GNSS receiver - were modeled for comparison.

The 3D models from Polycam were compared with those created using the Faro ScanArm Laser Line Probe (LLP). The scaling of the Polycam-generated models was ensured through a custom scale bar designed in Blender and fabricated by a 3D printer (Prusa Mini+). The geometry of the scale bar has been validated using the Faro ScanArm LLP against its nominal design.

While scale bars are not new in photogrammetric workflows, this methodology systematically integrates a low-cost, custom-printed, and independently validated 3D scale bar into smartphone-based 3D modeling. The quantitative verification of the scale bar prior to application ensures a traceable and reliable scaling process—an aspect often overlooked in low-cost photogrammetry workflows.

The workflow of this research demonstrates the validity of 3D models produced using smartphones, Mirrorless cameras, and Non-contact Portable Coordinate Measuring Machines (PCMMs), while a more detailed consideration was performed regarding their respective possibilities and limitations. The results clearly prove that smartphone-based 3D modeling is emerging as a friendly technology in use; its applicability in broader public circles is feasible; while at the same time pointing out its challenges in competing against professional systems.

Finally, the proposed methodology for using the custom-made 3D printed scale bar improves the accuracy of the rescaling process of the point cloud in comparison with the rescaling procedures recommended by the smartphone applications.

Key words: 3D modelling, Scale bar, Polycam, Non-contact probe, Mirrorless camera

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1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays (2025), various applications based on smartphone technology for 3D scanning and creating digital models are currently available and are being developed. The most widespread applications of this type are Luma AI, Scandy Pro, 3D Scanner App, KIRI Engine, MagiScan, Widar, Scanniverse, Qlone, RealityScan, Abound, Canvas, RoomScan Pro, and Polycam. A common feature of these applications is their low cost and their compatibility with a wide range of smartphones available on the market. Most of these applications use photogrammetric techniques to create 3D models of objects and spaces or even a combination of other technologies such as LiDAR, augmented reality (AR), and depth cameras. Among the various techniques, the dominant position is occupied by that of Structure from Motion (SfM).

The SfM problem in computer vision is the problem of recovering the three-dimensional structure of a stationary scene from a set of projective measurements, represented as a collection of two-dimensional (2D) images, via estimation of the motion of the cameras corresponding to these images. (Ozyesi, O. 2017)

While SfM is based on the mathematical models of photogrammetry, its primary distinction from traditional photogrammetry lies in its ability to extract 3D data from 2D overlapping images without requiring prior knowledge of the camera's calibration, position, orientation, or the presence of pre-established common points between images. Following the selection of images, the SfM algorithm automatically identifies common points and features within the overlapping image set. Consequently, the computed 3D coordinates, and thus the generated point cloud, exist in an arbitrary coordinate system without a defined scale. (Micheletti, N. et al.2019), (Iglhaut, J. et al.2019), (Westoby, M.J. et al. 2012)

Based on the algorithm of the SfM technology, a large set of well-overlapping and high-quality images, captured from various angles and distances around the object, is expected to improve the accuracy of the final result. A significant part of the quality of the results, also should depend on the characteristics of the studied object. If the object has transparent, reflective, or uniformly textured surfaces, the automatic identification of features becomes challenging and may lead to poor results. (Micheletti, N. et al. 2019), (Westoby, M.J. et al. 2012)

The main SfM steps as they are mentioned and described in detail in (Bianco, S. et al. 2018) are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Main steps of SfM photogrammetry technique

Regardless of which algorithms are used in each step, the final result is the generated point cloud with arbitrary scale. The Polycam application, which has been selected to be used in this research work, is also based on the general operating spirit of the SfM technique.

Polycam offers versatile 3D scanning with LiDAR and photogrammetry for high-quality models in 3D printing and CAD. It is user-friendly, optimized for mobiles, and can be used on **iOS and Android devices as well as web platforms**. Polycam enables both image acquisition and processing directly within its interface while also supporting the upload of external data for processing on its web platform. The generated 3D model can be created with varying densities to accommodate the specific needs of each project. It boasts faster processing options, hence ideal when on the go (no heavy equipment needed). Additionally, the final output can be

exported in multiple file formats for further processing. Regular updates and strong community support add much value in fields like architecture, e-commerce, and education. (Polycam Guide, 2025)

In order to rescale the produced point cloud, the Polycam application allows users to manually select a distance within the point cloud and input the corresponding known dimension. However, this procedure can introduce various errors, including those arising from the manual selection process and inaccuracies in the known distance. Therefore, in this study, the rescaling method differs significantly from the default approach offered by the Polycam application.

To evaluate the performance of this smartphone application, laser triangulation technology has been selected as reference. This technology forms the foundational operating principle for Non-contact PCMM, such as the Faro ScanArm, with the LLP. The laser triangulation methodology relies on the creation of a laser line, which is observed by a camera on the LLP. The laser line is generated by “fanning” out a laser light beam into a sheet-of-light. When that sheet-of-light intersects an object, a bright stripe of light can be seen on the surface of the object. The built-in camera views that stripe at an angle and the observed distortions can be translated into height variations. This is done many times in a second to quickly measure curved surfaces or surfaces that cannot be measured using a standard ball probe. (Faro Laser Line Probe, 2025), (Laser Line Scanning, 2025)

The Faro ScanArm LLP measurements have broad industrial applications in the need for 3D high-precision scanning and inspection. Especially, they ensure accuracy in body, frame, and assembly line inspections in the *automotive industry*. In *aerospace*, the applications involve component and turbine blade inspections, ensuring precision in manufacturing for fit. In *shipbuilding and marine industries*, Faro LLP measures hulls, decks, and large structures for fit and alignment. Faro LLP is used for structural inspections in construction and architecture, implant verification, prosthetics, and custom device verification in medical device manufacturing. This technology also regards component inspection, as well as in art and cultural heritage, where it can perform 3D scanning and can help in the artifact restoration. In conclusion, the Faro ScanArm LLP is a versatile tool for fast, accurate, and contactless measurements, which can be performed in almost every industry.

The result of the Faro ScanArm LLP approach is also a point cloud that is accurately positioned and scaled. The Faro ScanArm LLP specifications are illustrated in Figure 2. (Faro ScanArm Specifications, 2025) The high accuracy of the measured points using the LLP enables the produced point clouds of this technology to be used as reference data and by being compared with the point clouds that came from the Polycam application.

Figure 2. Faro ScanArm LLP specifications

While the use of scale bars for scale restoration in photogrammetric workflows is a known approach (Lankia, J. et al. 2024), (Nielsen, M.S. 2023), (Santagati, C. 2017), **this study contributes a practically validated and low-cost methodology for rescaling the smartphone-based 3D scanning.**

A custom-designed, 3D-printed scale bar is employed, whose geometry is independently verified using the high-precision Faro ScanArm LLP. **Unlike most low-cost workflows, this study explicitly quantifies the scale bar's geometric accuracy prior to application, adding reliability to the scale recovery process.**

In addition, unlike common low-cost photogrammetry workflows, in this study, the scale was not applied manually or based on single-axis proportional adjustments. Instead, a 7-parameter similarity transformation was used, which simultaneously corrects scale, rotation, and translation in three-dimensional space. This ensures accurate and uniform scale restoration across all axes, providing a robust geometric alignment. This approach surpasses simplified scaling methods that often consider only one dimension, significantly enhancing the reliability and precision of the final point cloud.

The proposed method offers a cost-effective and accessible scaling solution even for non-professional users who require reasonable accuracy in fields such as cultural heritage documentation, architecture, and education.

Furthermore, this study presents a detailed methodology combining the custom scale bar, a smartphone-based SfM workflow, and a robust alignment process using the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) algorithm to compare the resulting point clouds to the high-accuracy reference data. The methodology is tested across multiple objects with diverse materials and textures, highlighting both the potential and limitations of smartphone photogrammetry for practical applications.

By quantifying the scaling error, it is possible to distinguish its contribution from other sources, allowing a clearer evaluation of the factors affecting model accuracy.

The proposed approach offers a **low-cost and accessible solution** to improve the accuracy of smartphone-based 3D modelling, contributing to the growing need for flexible and affordable metrology tools in fields where even sub-millimeter precision is required.

2 METHODOLOGY

To achieve the previous goals, the next six steps must be followed in sequence (Figure 3):

1. **Object Scanning Using the Two Techniques**

With SfM and LLP Non-contact PCMM

2. **Manual Cleaning of Point Clouds**

In this step, the generated point clouds were cleaned to remove **unwanted surrounding objects** that were unintentionally captured during scanning. These typically included elements such as **the support structures or the background surface** that are not part of the object of interest. While automated noise filtering algorithms (e.g., statistical or radius-based outlier removal) are commonly used to handle random measurement noise, there is no information about the procedures that are followed internally by the smartphone application. So, in this study, **the cleaning process focused primarily on removing large, clearly distinguishable external objects, such as the object base or scanning platform.** Since these elements are easily identifiable, manual selection and deletion were preferred for precision and efficiency. In future applications for large-scale datasets, automatic segmentation techniques or background masking could be applied to streamline this process. CloudCompare, for instance, offers tools like clustering that can assist in isolating the object of interest and quickly removing extraneous parts of the scene.

3. Scaling the SfM Point Cloud

To achieve reliable scale restoration, a **physical scale bar containing multiple control points was included in each scanning setup with the SfM technology. These control points were specifically realized as spheres of known diameters, and the coordinates of the centres were precisely defined.** The use of spherical targets is advantageous, as their centres can be accurately calculated using best-fit sphere algorithms, minimizing the influence of point cloud noise or partial occlusions. The scale bar was captured within the same image dataset as the scanned object, allowing the selection of these sphere centre control points in the generated SfM point cloud. A similarity transformation (Ioannidou., S. 2020) was then applied to align the measured sphere centres with their known reference positions. This enabled the calculation of the scale factors that were subsequently applied in the SfM model. **Importantly, this process also provided an estimation of the scaling uncertainty.** By explicitly calculating the uncertainty of the scaling process, the method ensured traceability and improved the reliability of the subsequent geometric comparisons.

4. Fine Registration Using ICP Algorithm

After scaling the SfM point cloud, it is used as the “Data” for applying the ICP algorithm, with the LLP point cloud considered as the “Reference” data. ICP is an iterative process in which the registration error gradually decreases. The process stops either after a maximum number of iterations or when the error (RMS) difference between two iterations falls below a specified threshold.

5. Distance Computation Between Point Clouds

Once the two point clouds (SfM and LLP) are aligned as accurately as possible, the absolute distances between them are calculated. The default method for computing distances is the “nearest neighbour distance” for each point of the compared cloud. Here, the LLP point cloud serves as the “Reference”, and the SfM point cloud is the compared “Data”.

6. Evaluation of the SfM Point Cloud

The final steps involve visualizing the absolute distances using a colour scale and calculating the probability distribution of these distances. This allows estimating the percentage of absolute cloud-to-cloud distances that fall below specific thresholds, with the most important of these thresholds being the one that represents the scaling error.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the methodology

3 EXPERIMENT

For the experiments conducted in this study, the SfM photogrammetry technique was implemented using the Polycam application, while the Non-contact LLP method was employed with the Faro ScanArm.

Thus, the "Reference" point clouds of the objects were derived from the Faro ScanArm. Below is an image (Figure 4) taken during measurements using the LLP technique.

Figure 4. Scanning with Faro ScanArm

For the third stage of the methodology, which involves the correct scaling of the SfM point cloud, a custom 3D scale bar has been created. Its design is illustrated in Figure 5, and it consists of seven spheres with known centres, fabricated using the 3D printer Prusa Mini+ based on a digital model created in Blender. The diameters of spheres 1 and 2 are 8 mm, while the remaining five are 5 mm. For improved geometry, the spheres have been positioned at different heights. The theoretical coordinates of the spheres are also illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5. The theoretical model of the scale bar

Figure 6. The 3D printed scale bar

To verify the accuracy of the 3D-printed scale bar (Figure 6), it has also been scanned using the Faro ScanArm, and the resulting point cloud was processed with CloudCompare to calculate the sphere centres (best fit of points on a sphere). The seven measured sphere centres **underwent** a 6-parameter Helmert transformation (6 DOF, scale fixed) to align them with the theoretical coordinates. The transformed coordinates and the 3D distances between these and the theoretical centres are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Results of the 6 DOF transformation of scale bar

Point	X(m)	Y(m)	Z(m)	DX(mm)	DY(mm)	DZ(mm)	3DD(mm)
Sphere1	-0.027506	-0.000041	0.014923	-0.006	-0.041	-0.077	0.087
Sphere2	0.027433	0.000008	0.008976	-0.067	0.008	-0.024	0.071
Sphere3	0.015006	-0.022440	0.011971	0.006	0.060	-0.029	0.067
Sphere4	0.015006	0.022411	0.011983	0.006	-0.089	-0.017	0.091
Sphere5	-0.000038	0.000000	0.002594	-0.038	0.000	0.094	0.101
Sphere6	-0.012456	-0.012419	0.007554	0.044	0.082	0.054	0.108
Sphere7	-0.012446	0.012480	0.007499	0.054	-0.020	-0.001	0.058

The average 3D distance has been calculated in **83 μm** , which is deemed satisfactory. The scale bar must be photographed with the object of interest using Polycam. The scale bar can be reused unless damaged or if its geometric characteristics are suspected to have changed. To evaluate the developed methodology, its application has been tested on objects made of various materials with different textures:

1. A wooden owl. (Dimensions, L×W×H: 5 cm × 5 cm × 10 cm).
2. A clay pot. (Diameter: 14 cm, Height: 10 cm).
3. A plaster cast of Aphrodite of Milos. (Dimensions, L×W×H: 40 cm × 30 cm × 40 cm).
4. A plastic GNSS Trimble 5800 antenna. (Diameter: 18 cm, height: 7 cm).

The Polycam application has been selected for SfM technique implementation, supporting both smartphone use and web platform for processing photos from any digital camera. The images have been captured with the following means:

1. A Nikon Z 50 Mirrorless digital camera. Image size 5568 x 3712 pixels. Auto or Manual Mode.
2. A Samsung A52 5G smartphone. Image size 2124 x 2832 pixels.
3. An iPhone 16 Pro Max smartphone. Image size 2124 x 2832 pixels.

Every camera has three fundamental parameters that determine the total amount of light reaching its sensor, which ultimately influences the outcome of the final photograph. These parameters are ISO, aperture, and shutter speed. To be more specific, ISO indicates how sensitive a camera is to light. A lower ISO value is preferable because it allows the camera to capture images in low-light conditions more effectively. The aperture of the camera's lens refers to the size of the opening through which light enters. A smaller aperture results in less light hitting the sensor, while a larger aperture allows more light to pass through. Shutter speed refers to how quickly or slowly the shutter closes when taking a photograph, influencing the exposure time of the camera's sensor to light. (Pavlidis, G. 2022)

The Nikon Z50 camera gives users the ability to allow the camera to automatically adjust these parameters during a photography session, based on the environmental light conditions, which occurs in Auto Mode (The Dial Mode, 2025). Conversely, in Manual Mode, the user can choose specific settings. In this experiment, the settings that were used were: ISO 320, Shutter Speed 1/160, and Aperture f/8.

The objects that have been scanned (“Data” - SfM point clouds) using the three photographic sensors (combinations of object/sensor) are presented in Table 2. The “Reference” point cloud of each object has been obtained from the use of the Faro ScanArm.

In addition, the open-source software CloudCompare has been used for the processing of the point clouds, while a custom application (in MATLAB) has been employed to calculate the correct scale of the point clouds from the photogrammetric SfM technique. This custom application performed a 7-parameter affine transformation between the theoretical coordinate values of the centres of the scale bar spheres and the corresponding values derived from SfM. The calculated scale factors were then applied to the SfM point cloud in CloudCompare software. In Table 2, these scale values (unitless) for each scan are presented.

Table 2. Values of Scales per 7 DOF transformation

Object	Photos From	Description	Scale	σ (\pm)
Wooden Owl	Nikon Z 50	Auto Settings - 579 Photos	1.078680	0.001024
	Nikon Z 50	Manual Settings - 912 Photos	0.963564	0.000492
	Samsung A52 5G	380 Photos	0.152320	0.000246
	Samsung A52 5G	444 Photos	0.134823	0.000112
	iPhone 16 Pro Max	304 Photos	1.009936	0.000849

Clay Pot	Nikon Z 50	Manual Settings - 178 Photos	0.220691	0.000219
	Nikon Z 50	Manual Settings - 712 Photos	0.172442	0.000150
	Samsung A52 5G	300 Photos	0.983986	0.000130
	Samsung A52 5G	320 Photos	0.169030	0.000160
	iPhone 16 Pro Max	411 Photos	0.997109	0.000232
Plaster Cast of Aphrodite	Nikon Z 50	777 Photos	0.268124	0.000194
	Samsung A52 5G	817 Photos	0.226946	0.000288
	Samsung A52 5G	584 Photos	0.198761	0.000173
Plastic GNSS Antenna	Nikon Z 50	Manual Settings - 510 Photos	0.993784	0.000115
	Samsung A52 5G	507 Photos	1.023141	0.000247
	Samsung A52 5G	820 Photos	0.980216	0.000268

Due to the error in scale and the maximum dimension of each object, the maximum error in SfM point clouds that can be justified by the rescaling is illustrated in the next table. By studying the last column of Table 3, it is clear that from the 14 implementations of the methodology with the different combinations of object/sensor, the maximum error from the rescale process is almost 0.112 mm which is not so different than the deviation of the printed scale bar from its theoretical design in Blender (0.083 mm) taking into account the maximum dimension of the objects.

Table 3. The maximum error in SfM point clouds due to rescale

Object	Photos From	Description	Max Dimension (mm)	Error (mm)
Wooden Owl	Nikon Z 50	Auto Settings - 579 Photos		0.102
	Nikon Z 50	Manual Settings - 912 Photos		0.049
	Samsung A52 5G	380 Photos	100	0.025
	Samsung A52 5G	444 Photos		0.011
	iPhone 16 Pro Max	304 Photos		0.085
Clay Pot	Nikon Z 50	Manual Settings - 178 Photos		0.031
	Nikon Z 50	Manual Settings - 712 Photos		0.021
	Samsung A52 5G	300 Photos	140	0.018
	Samsung A52 5G	320 Photos		0.022
	iPhone 16 Pro Max	411 Photos		0.032
Plaster Cast of Aphrodite	Nikon Z 50	777 Photos		0.078
	Samsung A52 5G	817 Photos	400	0.112
	Samsung A52 5G	584 Photos		0.069
GNSS Antenna	Nikon Z 50	Manual Settings - 510 Photos		0.021
	Samsung A52 5G	507 Photos	180	0.044
	Samsung A52 5G	820 Photos		0.048

After the scale restoration of each point cloud, fine registration was performed using the ICP algorithm available in CloudCompare software. In this process, the user selects the “Reference” point cloud (LLP point cloud, which remains stationary) and the “Data” point cloud (SfM point cloud, which will eventually be aligned) for final registration of the two point clouds. The ICP algorithm is iterative, gradually reducing the registration error (ICP Algorithm in CloudCompare, 2025). Using the CloudCompare fine registration tool, the iterative process stops either after a maximum number of iterations or when the root mean square (RMS) error difference between two iterations drops below a specified threshold. In this study, the threshold was set to 83 μ m, representing the average “deviation” of the custom scale bar from its theoretical design.

Following the fine registration step for each point cloud of the object (SfM Point Cloud) with the corresponding reference point cloud (LLP Point Cloud), another tool of CloudCompare software has been utilized. Using the “CloudToCloud” Distance tool in the CloudCompare software, the distances between the two point clouds have been calculated. And in this process, the LLP point cloud is used as the “Reference,” while the distances are computed for the compared cloud (SfM Point Clouds). For the “CloudToCloud” distance computation, the nearest neighbour distance has been used. (Cloud To Cloud Distance in CloudCompare, 2025)

4 RESULTS

From the computation of the distances during the comparison of the point clouds (SfM) with their respective reference (LLP), colored point clouds have been created using Scalar Fields, with classification based on the calculated distances. These graphical approaches offer a quick and intuitive visualization of the results. Some of them are illustrated in Figures 7 & 8.

Figure 7. C2C absolute distances (m)
(Wooden Owl-Samsung A52 5G-444 Photos)

Figure 8. C2C absolute distances (m)
(Plaster Cast of Aphrodite-Samsung A52 5G-817 Photos)

A more detailed examination and analysis of the results led to the creation of the following table, which shows the percentage of points per scan whose “CloudToCloud” distances (SfM – LLP) fall below specific values.

Table 1. Percentage of points per scan whose C2C distances fall below specific values

Object	Photos From	Description	Number Of Points	Under 0.2mm (%)	Under 0.5mm (%)	Under 1mm (%)
Wooden Owl	Nikon Z 50	Auto Settings -	2254596	47	84	97
	Nikon Z 50	Manual Settings -	2791231	38	80	95
	Samsung A52 5G	380 Photos	3108132	38	80	95
	Samsung A52 5G	444 Photos	2868960	36	82	97
	iPhone 16 Pro	304 Photos	2298709	11	37	86
Clay Pot	Nikon Z 50	Manual Settings -	5468136	20	52	76
	Nikon Z 50	Manual Settings -	8860374	42	79	96
	Samsung A52 5G	300 Photos	7309899	12	30	64
	Samsung A52 5G	320 Photos	8295937	12	30	63
	iPhone 16 Pro	411 Photos	10170799	37	74	97
Plaster Cast of Aphrodite	Nikon Z 50	Manual Settings -	9660427	16	34	60
	Samsung A52 5G	817 Photos	9611489	12	28	51
	Samsung A52 5G	584 Photos	7660789	11	19	33
Plastic	Nikon Z 50	Manual Settings -	14172002	20	58	88
	Samsung A52 5G	507 Photos	13829372	26	62	90
	Samsung A52 5G	820 Photos	17381139	36	73	90

In the case of the wooden owl, the results of the Nikon Z50 were the best, with 97% of points falling inside 1 mm, though only 47% were within 0.2 mm, bringing out slight discrepancies from the reference model. While for the clay pot, the iPhone 16 Pro Max gave results that were considered the most precise among smartphones, 97% within 1 mm.

More complicated surfaces, such as the plaster cast of Aphrodite, posed greater challenges: only 48% (on average) of points were within 1 mm, regardless of the sensor that was used. When the number of photos has been reduced by 200 photos, only 33% of points were within 1 mm. Although of relatively simple geometry, the GNSS antenna showed lower accuracy likely due to its reflective surface on top, which caused inconsistencies in the scanning process or its uniform structure, which posed challenges for the automatic feature identification algorithm in SfM technology. Only 20% of points were within 0.2 mm, with the Nikon Z50.

For an even clearer representation of the scan comparison results with their respective reference scans, cumulative probability diagrams of the “CloudToCloud” distances were generated for each object using a custom application in MATLAB.

Figure 9. Cumulative Probability Plot for GNSS antenna results

Figure 10. Cumulative Probability Plot for wooden owl results

Figure 11. Cumulative Probability Plot for clay pot results

Figure 12. Cumulative Probability Plot for plaster cast of Aphrodite results

An overall comparison between the maximum scaling errors presented in Table 3 and the cloud-to-cloud distance distributions reveals a general correlation between lower scaling errors and higher proportions of points within smaller distance thresholds. This suggests that the precision of the scaling step contributes significantly to the overall geometric agreement between the smartphone-based and reference point clouds.

However, it is also evident that scale error is not the sole factor determining point cloud accuracy. Factors such as image acquisition quality, object texture, and surface complexity also play critical roles. For example, some scans with relatively low scaling errors still demonstrated moderate point cloud deviations, likely due to challenges in surface feature detection or insufficient photo coverage.

This indicates that while the scaling process is foundational to achieving good alignment, a holistic approach considering image quality, acquisition strategy, and object characteristics is necessary to optimize the overall accuracy.

Figures 9-12 clearly demonstrate that both the material properties and the scaling accuracy influence the quality of the final 3D reconstructions, but with a different degree of impact. The wooden owl, despite its relatively simple geometry, presented challenges due to its glossy surface, which introduced reflections and lighting inconsistencies that affected the SfM process. Although the scale error for this scan was carefully calculated and found to be extremely low (on the order of hundredths of a mm), the observed deviations in the point cloud were significantly larger, clearly indicating that surface reflectivity—not scale error—was the primary source of inaccuracies. Similarly, the plaster cast of Aphrodite, which had a matte surface but complex geometry, exhibited one of the smallest scale errors (maximum justified deviation of approximately 0.112 mm), yet the final comparison with the reference point cloud revealed substantial differences. This confirms that even when the scale error is quantitatively minimized and cannot explain deviations larger than tenths of a mm, the object's geometry and photogrammetric challenges dominate the final accuracy. The clay pot, with its semi-rough, non-reflective surface and regular cylindrical shape, showed moderate deviations. Although the scale error was again small and well-controlled, the lack of rich surface features and the repetitive geometry limited the effectiveness of the SfM feature detection and matching. The GNSS antenna was the most problematic object due to its highly reflective and smooth surface. Despite achieving a minimal scaling error, the SfM reconstruction deviated significantly from the reference, confirming that material properties such as reflectivity can cause systematic errors that cannot be corrected by precise scaling. Overall, the results confirm that the scaling error, which was rigorously quantified in this study, contributes only marginally to the total point cloud deviation. The primary factors affecting photogrammetric accuracy are the material characteristics, surface texture, and geometric complexity of the scanned objects.

For example, in the case of the plaster cast of Aphrodite, despite achieving a very low scaling error (maximum justified scaling deviation of 0.112 mm), the comparison with the reference point cloud revealed that only 12% of the points were within 0.2 mm and just 51% were within 1 mm. This highlights that even with accurate scaling, significant geometric deviations can occur due to the object's complex surface geometry and potential challenges in feature detection by the SfM algorithm. This example confirms that scaling precision alone does not guarantee overall point cloud accuracy—object characteristics and image acquisition strategy are equally critical factors.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the accuracy and practical potential of smartphone-based 3D modeling using Polycam, compared to high-precision Non-contact PCMM. The core question was whether low-cost photogrammetry (from a smartphone) can provide reliable geometric data for metrological applications.

The results showed that while smartphone-based photogrammetry can produce acceptable models for visual purposes, it cannot yet compete with professional systems in terms of precision. A key contribution of this research was the integration of a validated, custom 3D-printed scale bar into the workflow, providing a traceable and quantifiable scale restoration. However, the scaling error, although carefully calculated, was found to contribute minimally to the overall deviations. Instead, surface properties such as reflectivity, texture richness, and object complexity were the dominant factors affecting model accuracy.

The key point is that **accurate scaling alone is not sufficient** to ensure geometric reliability in smartphone photogrammetry. The object's material and the photo acquisition strategy play a decisive role. Despite its limitations, smartphone-based 3D modeling remains a promising, low-cost solution for applications where even sub-millimeter accuracy is critical, such as cultural heritage, education, and preliminary assessments.

Future research should focus on improving the reconstruction of reflective and complex surfaces, enhancing feature detection, and optimizing the scaling process in all spatial directions. This study offers a validated, accessible methodology, while also defining the boundaries and possibilities of smartphone-based 3D scanning today.

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